

CLASSIFICATION OF ENGLISH COLLOCATIONS AND PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATING THEM INTO UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *The present article aims to discuss issues that translators and English language learners face while interpreting English phraseological units, particularly collocations. Translating is more than knowing of language, the translator must be creative and should have high linguistic and aesthetic skills to describe complicated phrases correctly. This paper is devoted to showing the ways and methods of eliminating these crucial problems in the translation process.*

Keywords: *descriptive translation, target language, grammatical collocation, lexical collocations, strong collocutors, weak collocutors, fixed phrase, word formation.*

КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ АНГЛИЙСКИХ СЛОВСОЧЕТАНИЙ И ПРОБЛЕМЫ ИХ ПЕРЕВОДА НА УЗБЕКСКИЙ ЯЗЫК

Аннотация. *Цель настоящей статьи - обсудить проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются переводчики и изучающие английский язык при переводе английских фразеологизмов, в частности словосочетаний. Перевод - это нечто большее, чем знание языка, переводчик должен быть творческим человеком и обладать высокими лингвистическими и эстетическими навыками, чтобы правильно описывать сложные фразы. Эта статья посвящена показу путей и методов устранения этих важнейших проблем в процессе перевода.*

Ключевые слова: *описательный перевод, целевой язык, грамматические словосочетания, лексические словосочетания, сильные словосочетания, слабые словосочетания, фиксированная фраза, словообразование.*

English and Uzbek collocations distinctly differ from each other, for that reason interpreting them from the target language to the source language may be challenging, and also demands a high level of language skill. One of the main tasks of the translator is to preserve the real meaning of phrases despite linguistic, semantic, and grammatical differences between languages.

Numerous researches have been carried out on translating collocations. For instance, Lyons (1997) believes that a collocation should be considered as a whole and that separating its components does not give a legitimate meaning equal to the combination of them.

So many collocations are unique as well as culturally specific, if they are translated word for word, it can sound unnatural and can cause more confusion. Therefore, in some cases, descriptive translation may be handled with them, during this process one or more elements of phrases can be omitted. Although previous research on this topic has been done in detail, insufficient attention has been paid to the linguistic meaning and classification of collocations.

The main objective of this paper is to assist readers in interpreting some English phrases that are hard to find suitable equivalents in the Uzbek language.

This article will first discuss several examples of complex collocations in English, and then tackle the issues of translating them into the Uzbek language.

First of all, collocations are classified by "lexical collocation" and "grammatical collocation".

Grammatical collocations are:

- noun plus preposition; comment on something.
- verb plus preposition; involve in something.
- adjective plus preposition; fond of something.

Translating grammatical collocations to the Uzbek language is much more intricate than interpreting lexical ones, owing to variations in the grammatical structure of the two languages.

For instance, the phrase guilty of something is translated as "biror narsada aybdor". The preposition "of" is interpreted differently,

Let us take other illustrations of grammatical collocations:

- by chance means "tasodifan";
- by dint of means "tufayli, sababli"

The preposition "by" changes the direct meaning of other words combined with itself.

- in charge means "javobgar"
- at rest, the meaning of this phrase is "dead or free from pain and problems", another explanation of it is "steady, not mowing". In the translation, it is necessary to pay close attention to even minor elements of each phrase, otherwise, the compound may depict completely different words.

Here, we take two examples of slightly different collocations.

- fresh out of something means "just finished one's education and not having a lot of experience" or "just come from a particular place"

- be fresh out of something - "used last supplied of something" (American English spoken) e.g., Anna is fresh out of juice - "Anna sharbatning oxirini ichdi".

Lexical collocations may be weak and strong, weak ones can collocate hundreds of words, therefore, they are termed "weak collocations"

Strong collocations are often so-called "fixed phrases" by some scientists because they cannot be used together with other synonyms of words. In terms of the degree of cohesiveness of lexical combination, Benson (1986) states collocations are "fixed phrases" stored in the mind.

Strong collocator

Weak collocator

- wish
Make
Fulfil + wish
Express

Big + price, river, flat, queue, station,
corpus, university, disappointment and
etcetera

Only a few words can come together with "wish", which makes it a strong collocator

Big is used together with several words, therefore it is a weak collocator.

Other examples of strong and weak collocations:

Weak collocations:

1. enormous + truck, house, airport, cup, place, machine, hospital, tree;
2. deeply + disappointed, concerned, unhappy, regretful, moved, hurt, shocked;
3. straight + hair, way, order, fence, line.

Strong collocations:

4. blissfully ignorant - happy because they do not know about the danger, e.g. The workers of the factory are blissfully ignorant about the danger of being unemployed. The word "blissfully" totally changed the meaning of the accompanying word, and this phrase has a figurative meaning;
5. do harm (we cannot use make or have instead of do, it is a fixed phrase) is translated into Uzbek language as "zarar keltirmoq/ziyon qilmoq";
6. a nuclear family (this is too strong collocation, nuclear has completely changed its real meaning), is a family that consists of only a husband, wife, and children.

In general, there are seven main types of collocations:

Adjective + noun

7. key issue = 'asosiy muommo";
8. particular feature = "alohida xususiyat".

Noun + noun

9. a pang of nostalgia = "o'tmishdagi xotiralarni yodga olish";
10. travel arrangement = "sayohatni tashkil qilish".

Verb + noun

11. make progress = "rivojlanmoq, taraqqiyotga erishmoq";
12. go grey = "oqarib ketmoq" (asosan sochga nisbatan qo'llaniladi).

Adverb + adjective

13. immaculately groomed - tidy and looked after with great care;
14. utterly ridiculous = "mutlaqo kulguli".

Collocation with prepositional phrases.

15. keen on = "ishtiyomand";
16. by cash = "naqd pul orqali".

Verb + adverb

17. place gently = "muloyimlik bilan qo'yimoq";
18. rely heavily = "judayam qattiq tayanmoq".

Adverb + Verb

19. vividly remember = "aniq eslamoq";
20. hotly deny = "qattiq rad etmoq".

We have discussed various types and examples of expressions, and now let's talk about how to translate them easily and retain them quickly.

Why do English learners need to learn phraseological units?

The main reason why learners must make a special effort to acquire collocation is that they are a natural part of the English language. The natural use of phrases is an indication of a person's general English proficiency.

Sometimes learners spend hours and hours learning separate words, however, they hardly pay attention to words that are commonly used together.

Acquiring them together rather than in isolation is the best way to remember more easily. Furthermore, it is vital to take note of phrases that have been read in each context.

Reading as many books as possible not only broadens one's outlook but also assists in remembering words together.

"Understanding terminology, organizing or analyzing lexical accumulations in one or two articles is quite impossible. It is essential to conduct both theoretical and practical research on them. Halliday and Hasan (1976) treat collocation as words used in the lexical cohesion of text and contain "a cohesive force". Taking the pragmatic view of collocation, Nattinger and DeCarrico (1992) consider collocations as high-frequency word combinations. Translators must identify the grammatical difficulties they face during the translation process from one language to another. Their ideas on this topic are completely right and are proven by several survey-based researches. The structure of the Uzbek and English languages, their linguistic family affiliation, word formation, and grammatical and lexical aspects differ significantly. Of course, every translator must take these differences into account. Additionally, to achieve accurate translation without falling into the mentioned problems, a translator needs to be well acquainted with each aspect of the language"

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